

A Comparative Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Iron Folic Acid Tablets Supplementation During Menstruation Among the Adolescent Girls Studying in Selected Colleges (MP)

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ABSTRACT

Iron deficiency is the most widespread nutritional problem in the world. More than two billion women are estimated to suffer from iron deficiency, mostly in developing countries. The prevalence of anemia is commonly seen due to severe iron deficiency in a population. The M.P. State government has accepted anemia as one of the major reasons of high MMR in the state. Nearly 46.9 per cent urban and 59.6 per cent rural women population in state are anemic.

The aim of the study is to assess the effectiveness of Iron Folic Acid tablets supplementation during menstrual period among the adolescent girls studying in selected colleges (M.P).

Pre-test post-test control group design with true experimental approach was adopted to evaluate the study. The sample consist of 100 adolescent girls studying in selected college. Random sampling technique was used for the selection of the participants.

The result of the study revealed that the post-test Hb level of experimental group has increased by 38%, Hb level stabilized in 28% cases and Hb level remained low in 34% cases. The total difference in pre-test score mean is 11.134 and SD is 0.90 and post-test score mean is 11.198 and SD is 0.64 in experimental group.

KEY WORDS: adolescent girls, haemoglobin level, iron folic acid supplementation, menstrual period.

INTRODUCTION:

Iron deficiency is the most widespread nutritional problem in the world. More than two billion people are estimated to suffer from iron deficiency, mostly in developing countries.

The M.P. State government has stated that Anemia is one of the major reasons of high MMR in the state. According to state assembly revelations, state had 335 MMR (per 1 lakh live births) during the year 2014-16 as per Sample Registration Survey (SRS) and it declined to 310 MMR in the year 2007-09 as per the Annual Health Survey, 2010.

As per the personal experience of the researcher, during posting in community and urban

areas, the researcher found that there is high prevalence of iron deficiency Anemia among adolescent girls augmented with poor eating habits, which reflects their poor status of nutrition.

For combating this anemic problem of adolescent girls, Government of India Implemented weekly Iron Folic acid tablets supplementation to the school going girls.

The main objective of the study was to assess the effectiveness of Iron Folic acid tablet supplementation during menstruation period.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To assess the pre haemoglobin level of adolescent girls.
2. To administer Iron Folic Acid tablets (100 mg) supplementation during menstrual period among adolescent girls.
3. To assess the post haemoglobin level of adolescent girls

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4. To evaluate the effectiveness of iron folic acid tablets supplementation during menstruation period among the adolescent girls of experimental group.
5. To find out the difference between post haemoglobin level of both experimental and control group.

HYPOTHESIS:

H₀: There is no significant difference in Hb level after implementation of iron folic acid supplementation among adolescent girls during menstruation period

H₁: There is significant difference in Hb level after implementation of iron folic acid supplementation among adolescent girls during menstruation period in experimental group.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

- **Research approach:** Quantitative research approach was used.
- **Research design:** Pre test post-test control group research design was used.
- **Independent variable:** administration of iron & folic acid tablets supplementation among adolescent girls is independent variable.
- **Dependent variable:** The Hb level of adolescent girls is dependent variable.
- **Research setting:** The study was conducted in selected
- **Population:** The target population is adolescent girls.
- **Sample size:** 100 adolescent girls studied in selected colleges.
- **Sampling Technique:** Random sampling technique was used for the study.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION:

Ethical clearance obtained from the institutional ethics committee.

RESULTS:

The findings of the study revealed that the Hb level of experimental group has increased in 38% of cases.

Finding related to post test score of Hb level of control group-

According to the findings the Hb level of control group in that 18% (9) have increased hb level, 12% (6) have stable Hb level and 70 % (35) have decrease hb level.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of socio demographic variables of Participants (n=100).

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-19	63	63%
20-21	37	37%
Religion		
Hindu	60	60%
Muslim	12	12%
Christian	9	9%
Others	19	19%
Place of residence		
Urban	70	70%
Rural	30	30%
Dietary Patten		
Vegetarian	34	34%
Non vegetarian	66	66%
Duration of Menstruation Cycle		
1-3 days	30	30%
4-5 days	62	62%
6-7 days	3	3%
More than 7 days	5	5%
Duration of Menstruation period		
Less than 28 days	51	51%
28 days	17	17%
More than 28 days	42	42%

Finding related to Effectiveness of iron tablets supplementation during menstruation period among adolescent girls of experimental group.

The findings of the study revealed pre-test score of Hb level and post test score of Hb level and difference of experimental group participants. In this the mean is 11.134 and SD is 0.90 in the pre - test of experimental group and in post- test experimental group mean is 11.98 and SD is 0.64, t value is 0.709 and p value is <0.0001.

Findings related to difference between post hb level of experimental and control group.

In the study findings, the post test score of Hb level difference of experimental group mean is 11.198 and SD is 0.641 and in control group participants mean value is 10.714 and SD is 0.682. t value is 28.47 and p value is < 0.005 and significant using unpaired t test.

Table 2: Show the Post-test score of Hb level in experimental and control group.

Hb level	Experimental group		Control group	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Increased	19	38%	9	18%
Stable	14	28%	6	12%
Decreased	17	34%	35	70%
TOTAL	50	100%	50	100%

Table 3: Effectiveness of iron tablets supplementation during menstruation period among adolescent girls of experimental group.

Hb level score	Mean	SD	N	t-test value	p value
pre-test experimental group	11.134	0.9	50	0.709	<0.0001
Post-test experimental group	11.198	0.64	50		

Table 4: Difference between post Hb level of experimental and control group.

Hb level score	Mean	SD	N	Unpaired t test	p value
Post-test experimental group	11.198	0.641	50	28.47	< 0.005
Post-test control group	10.714	0.682	50		

After completing the study control group adolescent girls also received the Iron folic acid tablets supplementation for three months.

CONCLUSION:

The above study showed that the Supplementation of Iron Folic acid tablet during menstruation period is helpful in preventing and maintaining Hb level among adolescent girls .

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